

Steady-state heat conduction in nuclear fuel: convergence analysis of a novel method, applied to cylindrical and Cartesian geometries

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ABSTRACT

In reactor multiphysics modelling and simulation, accurate determination of the fuel temperature profile is essential to evaluate key feedback mechanisms, such as Doppler feedback, in safety analyses. In the present work, a numerical approach is proposed and applied to cylindrical and Cartesian geometries. The obtained solution is compared, for a set of boundary conditions, to the one computed using the finite difference method, typically used in a simplified thermal-hydraulic code available at CEA. The results suggest that the presented method requires lower computational cost and memory to achieve a targeted accuracy. The approach, implemented in a dedicated Python module, is being considered as a viable option for integration into CEA multiphysics simulation tools for performance gain.

Keywords: Stationary heat equation, Kirchhoff transformation, convergence analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear reactors are complex multiphysics systems, whose behaviour is the result of the interplay of several processes, including neutron transport, heat transfer, fluid dynamics and thermomechanics, to name a few. In particular, neutron cross-sections depend both on the kinetic energy of the incident neutron and the medium temperature. In pressurized water reactors (PWRs), if the fuel temperature increases, a prompt negative feedback is observed, due to an increase in ^{238}U absorption reaction rate (Doppler effect).

To address the calculation of the fuel temperature profile, whether for simplified thermal analysis or detailed fuel performance assessment, a variety of numerical methods are available in scientific literature [1]. For instance, in the simplified thermal-hydraulics module of APOLLO3® [2], namely THEDI [3], the heat equation is discretized by the finite-difference method. Depending on fuel heat generation, thermal conductivity and boundary conditions, the temperature profile may be affected by steep gradients. Finite difference schemes represent derivatives by discrete difference quotients, thus necessitating fine grids to achieve satisfying accuracy, which in turn leads to increased computational cost and memory requirements.

The obtained solution remains acceptable for industrial-like calculations using coarse discretization (e.g., 1 to 4 representative fuel rods per assembly). In order to improve code performance, in particular for multiphysics calculations adopting finer discretization (e.g., at pin level), a discussion has been started around the possibility to update the 1D heat transfer module of THEDI, by investigating a novel approach to compute the fuel temperature distribution, with fewer meshes, without compromising numerical accuracy. The illustrated method recalls the one proposed in [4], sharing some similarities, e.g., both algorithms are based on the analytical determination of the thermal flux and Kirchhoff transformation formalism, [5]. Nevertheless, the presented work targets both cylindrical and planar geometries,

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both with mixed Neumann-Dirichlet and pure Dirichlet boundary conditions. The paper provides a detailed analysis of the convergence rate. The results obtained with the new method are systematically compared to the ones of finite differences, to assess the advantages of the proposed strategy, as a first step toward potential implementation in the multiphysics platform of CEA.

This work is structured as follows. In Sec. 2, the stationary heat conduction equation is briefly recalled. In Sec. 3, the equation is solved for the heat flux, with mixed Neumann-Dirichlet boundary conditions and piece-wise volumetric source, in cylindrical geometry. In Secs. 3-4, the heat equation is discretized to determine the temperature profile, in cylindrical and Cartesian geometry, with two sets of boundary conditions. The convergence rate is discussed for each case and compared to the reference solution, obtained by finite differences. A practical application to a fuel rod is illustrated in Sec. 5. Finally, in Sec. 6, prospects for implementation in the CEA multiphysics platform are mentioned.

2. STEADY-STATE HEAT CONDUCTION

The stationary heat equation may be expressed as

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = s(\mathbf{r}), \quad \mathbf{r} \in V, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{q}(\mathbf{r})$ represents the heat flow per unit surface and time $\left[\frac{W}{m^2}\right]$ and $s(\mathbf{r})$ is the volumetric source $\left[\frac{W}{m^3}\right]$. Fourier's law of heat conduction [6] reads as

$$\mathbf{q} = -k \nabla T(\mathbf{r}), \quad (2)$$

where $k = k(T)$ is the thermal conductivity $\left[\frac{W}{m \cdot K}\right]$, which depends on the local temperature, T .

3. APPLICATION TO CYLINDRICAL GEOMETRY

Let V be an infinite cylinder, centred in 0, with radius $r = r_f$. Assuming the azimuthal symmetry holds, i.e., $T = T(r)$, let us set mixed Neumann-Dirichlet boundary conditions, with null heat flux along the cylinder axis, i.e., $q(0) = 0$, and known temperature on the border, namely $T(r_f) = T_f$. For the stated problem, the thermal flux has an analytical expression for several types of volumetric source distributions. For instance, assuming s is a piece-wise function, of the kind

$$s(r) = \sum_{n=1}^N s_n \cdot (H(r - r_{n-1}) - H(r - r_n)), \quad (3)$$

where H is the Heaviside function, and $s_n \geq 0, \forall n = 1, \dots, N$, with $0 \equiv r_0 < r_1 \leq \dots \leq r_n \leq \dots \leq r_N \equiv r_f$, one has

$$q(r) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} r_i^2 (s_i - s_{i+1}) + s_n r \right), \quad r \in [r_{n-1}, r_n]. \quad (4)$$

Eq. (2) may be integrated over $[r, r_f]$, with $0 \leq r \leq r_f$. After variable change, one obtains

$$\int_{T(r)}^{T(r_f)} -k(T) dT = \int_r^{r_f} q(r) dr, \quad (5)$$

which is known as the Kirchhoff transformation [5]. Generally speaking, as the thermal conductivity depends on the temperature, Eq. (5) does not have analytical solutions.

3.1. Numerical solution with mixed Neumann-Dirichlet boundary conditions

For the sake of simplicity, let us assume that the volumetric source is uniform throughout the fuel pellet cross-section. Note that the approach may be easily generalised to a generic source distribution. One-dimensional heat conduction is solved along the inward direction, from $r = r_N = r_f$ to $r = r_0 = 0$, by successive fixed-point iterations. Eq. (5) is solved over two nested loops, of index i and n , respectively

$$\begin{cases} T_n^{(i+1)} = T_{n+1} + \frac{1}{4 \kappa_n^{(i)}} s (r_{n+1}^2 - r_n^2), \\ T_n^{(0)} = T_N \equiv T_f, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with $n = 0, \dots, N - 1$ and $i = 0, \dots, M$, i being the iteration index, and $T_n \equiv T(r_n)$. Eq. (5) left-hand side integral is initialised as

$$\kappa_n^{(0)} = \frac{1}{2} (k(T_{n+1}) + k(T_n^{(0)})). \quad (7)$$

For later iterations, $\kappa_n^{(i)}$ is computed via the `integrate.quad` function of the SciPy Python library [7], which returns the result of the numerical integration over the interval $[T_{n+1}, T_n^{(i)}]$. For optimisation reasons, the innermost loop runs over the fixed-point iteration index i . This choice is motivated observing that (1) the rate of convergence of each unknown, namely T_n , may not be equal to the others and (2), according to Eq. (6), T_n does not depend on any upstream term, namely T_{n-1} , with $n = 1, \dots, N - 1$.

In the following, let us suppose that the thermal conductivity is $k(T) = a + \frac{b}{T+c}$. Assuming $s = 1 \cdot 10^8 \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$, $T(r_f) = 1100^\circ\text{C}$, with $r_f = 0.399229 \text{ cm}$, thermal conductivity with parameters $a = 1.05$, $b = 2150$, $c = -73.15$, radial discretization composed of $N = 1, 5, 10, 20, 25$ radii of equal length, and error tolerance $\varepsilon = 1 \cdot 10^{-7}$, the proposed method converges in few iterations per mesh (6 iterations for $N = 1$), if the temperature is initialised to a flat profile, as in Eq. (6). The rate of convergence, defined in terms of number of radii N required to approach the asymptotic solution, has been investigated. The finite-difference solution with $N = 5 \cdot 10^7$, provided by a numerical mock-up (briefly described in App. A), is taken as the reference for the following analysis. In Fig. 1a, the relative error with respect to near-asymptotic finite differences is of the same order as the required precision (10^{-7}), for all discretisations, even for the one with $N = 1$, i.e., computing the sole fuel centre-line temperature. On the other hand, finite differences require a much finer radial mesh, in order to converge to the reference solution, as proven in Fig. 1b.

(a) Relative error (%) with respect to converged finite differences, as a function of the number of radii.

(b) Rate of convergence of finite differences, measured as the relative error with respect to the converged solution.

Figure 1. Infinite cylinder, with mixed Neumann-Dirichlet boundary conditions - convergence rate analysis.

3.2. Numerical solution with Dirichlet boundary conditions

In the present section, the heat equation is solved over a cylindrical shell with Dirichlet boundary conditions, given by the temperature on the innermost radius, namely $T(r_0) = T_0$, and the temperature on the outermost radius, i.e., $T(r_N) = T_f$, with $0 < r_0 < r_N \equiv r_f$. For the sake of simplicity, the volumetric source is assumed to be uniform throughout the fuel-pellet cross-section. The temperature distribution for a set of discrete radii may be computed using the sequence

$$\begin{cases} T_n^{(i+1)} = T_{n+1} + \frac{s}{4 \kappa_n^{(i)}} (r_{n+1}^2 - r_n^2) + \frac{c_1}{\kappa_n^{(i)}} \ln \frac{r_{n+1}}{r_n}, \forall n = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ T_n^{(0)} = \frac{T_N - T_0}{r_N - r_0} (r_n - r_0) + T_0, \forall n \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $c_1 = \frac{1}{\ln \frac{r_N}{r_0}} \left[\frac{s}{4} (r_0^2 - r_N^2) + a (T_N - T_0) + b \ln \frac{|T_N + c|}{|T_0 + c|} \right]$. In Eq. (8), the temperature profile is initialised by means of a linear distribution, assuming values T_0 and T_N , at $r = r_0$ and $r = r_N$, respectively. As in Subsec. 3.1, the unknowns $\{T_n\}$ are solved sequentially, converging the temperature at the current radius, before moving to the neighbouring mesh. In Eq. (8), we implicitly chose to sweep the cylindrical shell along the inward direction. Nevertheless, as the value of the temperature is also known at $r = 0$, the mesh may be equivalently swept in the outward direction, in order to retrieve the temperature profile. In Fig. 2a, the presented algorithm is compared to the finite-differences converged solution, using $N = 10^6$ radial meshes. The imposed error tolerance for convergence of the fixed-point iterations over index i (see Eq. (8)) is $\varepsilon = 10^{-7}$, in relative value. The relative error with respect to the reference solution is of the same order as the required precision, even for $N = 2$, where only the temperature at $r_1 = \frac{1}{2}(r_0 + r_f)$ is computed.

(a) Relative error (%) with respect to converged finite differences, as a function of the number of radii.

(b) Rate of convergence of finite differences, measured as the relative error with respect to the converged solution.

Figure 2. Infinite cylinder, with Dirichlet boundary conditions - convergence rate analysis.

4. APPLICATION TO PLANAR GEOMETRY

In the following, the stationary heat equation is solved over an infinite slab of thickness d , with mixed Neumann-Dirichlet (Subsec. 4.1) and pure Dirichlet boundary conditions (Subsec. 4.2), respectively.

4.1. Numerical solution with mixed Neumann-Dirichlet boundary conditions

Let us consider the boundary-value problem defined by

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = s, & x \in [0, d], \text{ with } d > 0, \\ q(x = 0) = 0, & T(x = d) = T_{ext}. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Based on symmetry arguments, one can prove that the heat flux is given by $q(x) = s \cdot x$. Let us discretise Eq. (5) over a set of ordered points $\{x_n\}_{n=0, \dots, N}$, with $0 = x_0 \leq \dots \leq x_n \leq \dots \leq x_N \equiv d$, which yields

$$\begin{cases} T_n^{(i)} = T_{n+1} + \frac{s \cdot (T_n^{(i-1)} - T_{n+1})}{2 \cdot \int_{T_{n+1}}^{T_n^{(i-1)}} k(T) dT} \cdot (x_{n+1}^2 - x_n^2), & \forall n = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ T_n^{(0)} = T_{ext}, & \forall n = 0, \dots, N, \\ T_n^{(1)} = T_{n+1} + \frac{1}{k(T_{ext}) + k(T_{n+1})} \cdot s \cdot (x_{n+1}^2 - x_n^2), & \forall n = 0, \dots, N-1. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

In Fig. 3a, the presented algorithm is compared to the finite-differences converged solution, which employs $N = 10^7$ meshes. As in Subsecs. 3.1-3.2, fixed-point iterations are terminated when the error, defined as $\epsilon_n = 1 - \frac{T_n^{(i)}}{T_n^{(i-1)}}$, $\forall n = 0, \dots, N-1$, falls below a predefined threshold ϵ . As in Figs. 1a-2a, ϵ is set to 10^{-7} . If just the temperature at the adiabatic wall is demanded, one may set $N = 1$, as the error is already below the imposed tolerance (Fig. 3a). On the contrary, finite differences suffer from slow convergence, as proven in Fig. 2b. The absolute error with respect to the converged solution reaches up to 7.9°C , if the slab is discretised into $N = 10^2$ meshes. For $N = 10$, the maximum error exceeds 74.7°C .

(a) Relative error (pcm) with respect to converged finite differences ($N = 10^7$), as a function of the number of computed points ($N = 1, 5, 10, 20, 25$).

(b) Rate of convergence of finite differences (from numerical mock-up), measured as the relative error with respect to the converged solution ($N = 10^7$).

Figure 3. Infinite slab, with mixed Neumann-Dirichlet boundary conditions - convergence rate analysis.

4.2. Numerical solution with pure Dirichlet boundary conditions

Let us consider the boundary-value problem defined by

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = s, & x \in [0, d], \text{ with } d > 0, \\ T(x = 0) = T_0, & T(x = d) = T_{ext}. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The general solution for the heat flux is given by $q(x) = q(0) + s \cdot x$. In order to determine $q(0)$, one may simply inject the analytic expression of q into Eq. (5), and integrate over the whole domain. Finally, following arguments similar to those in Subsec. 4.1, one obtains the following mathematical sequence:

$$\begin{cases} T_n^{(i)} = T_{n+1} + \frac{(T_n^{(i-1)} - T_{n+1})}{\int_{T_{n+1}}^{T_n^{(i-1)}} k(T) dT} \cdot \left(q(0) + \frac{s}{2} \cdot (x_{n+1} + x_n) \right) \cdot (x_{n+1} - x_n), & \forall n = 0, \dots, N-1 \\ T_n^{(0)} = \frac{T_N - T_0}{d} \cdot x_n + T_0, & \forall n = 0, \dots, N. \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

In Fig. 4a, the presented algorithm is compared to converged finite differences, using $N = 10^7$ meshes, for three discretisation levels, $N = 2, 5, 10$. The metrics used for the comparison are the relative error (solid lines) and absolute error (dashed lines) in the computed temperature values. The imposed tolerance is $\varepsilon = 10^{-7}$. The maximum absolute error is about $0.0012 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. In Fig. 4b, a similar comparison is carried out for finite differences, employing $N = 10^3, 10^4, 10^5$ meshes. For $N = 10^2$ (not in figure), the deviation from the converged solution reaches up to $16.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

(a) Relative error ((%), left axis, solid lines) and absolute error ($^\circ\text{C}$), right axis, dashed lines) with respect to converged finite differences, as a function of the number of computed points ($N - 1 = 1, 4, 9$).

(b) Rate of convergence of finite differences, with $N = 10^3, 10^4, 10^5$ radial meshes, evaluated as the relative error ((%), left axis, solid lines) and absolute error ($^\circ\text{C}$), right axis, dashed lines) with respect to the converged solution.

Figure 4. Infinite slab with Dirichlet boundary conditions - convergence rate analysis.

5. APPLICATION TO A FUEL ROD

Let us model a fuel rod, containing UO_2 , helium and Zircaloy, within $[0, r_f]$, $[r_f, r_g]$ and $[r_g, r_c]$, respectively, with $0 < r_f < r_g < r_c$. For the sake of simplicity, let us suppose that the power distribution is uniform in the fuel and the clad, and that no heat is produced in the gap. The associated boundary

value problem may be posed as

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} = s_f \cdot (H(r) - H(r - r_f)) + s_c \cdot (H(r - r_g) - H(r - r_c)), \\ q(r = 0) = 0, T(r = r_c) = T_{ext}, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

where H is the Heaviside function. One can prove that the heat flux reads as $q(r) = \frac{s_f \cdot r}{2}$, within $[0, r_f]$, and $q(r) = \frac{s_f \cdot r_f^2}{2r} + \frac{s_c \cdot (r^2 - r_g^2)}{2r}$, within $[r_g, r_c]$. In the clad, Eq. (5) may be discretised as follows:

$$\begin{cases} T_n^{(i)} = T_{n+1} + \frac{(T_n^{(i-1)} - T_{n+1})}{\int_{T_{n+1}}^{T_n^{(i-1)}} k(T) dT} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}(s_f \cdot r_f^2 - s_c \cdot r_g^2) \cdot \ln \frac{r_{n+1}}{r_n} + \frac{1}{4}s_c(r_{n+1}^2 - r_n^2) \right), \\ T_n^{(0)} = T_{ext}, \\ T_n^{(1)} = T_{n+1} + \frac{2}{k(T_{ext}) + k(T_{n+1})} \cdot \left(\frac{1}{2}(s_f \cdot r_f^2 - s_c \cdot r_g^2) \cdot \ln \frac{r_{n+1}}{r_n} + \frac{1}{4}s_c(r_{n+1}^2 - r_n^2) \right). \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In the fuel-clad gap, a linear relationship holds, which enables the computation of the external fuel temperature from the inner cladding temperature and the heat transfer coefficient of the gap, $h_{gap} [\frac{W}{m^2 \cdot ^\circ C}]$ [8]. In Fig. 5a-5b, the proposed method is compared to converged finite differences, using $N = 10^7$ meshes in the fuel and the clad and 10 meshes in the gap, for the coarsest mesh possible, i.e., the one computing only $T(0)$, $T(r_f)$ and $T(r_g)$. Once again the tolerance ε is set to 10^{-7} . The unknowns $T(0)$ and $T(r_g)$ converge in 11 and 4 fixed-point iterations, respectively. The observed relative error is of the same order as the imposed error tolerance.

(a) Fuel rod temperature profile. Comparison of the coarsest solution with converged finite differences.

(b) Relative and absolute error of the coarsest solution with respect to converged finite differences.

Figure 5. Fuel rod, with Neumann-Dirichlet boundary conditions.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This study aims to assess the potential for replacing the finite-difference method with an alternative numerical approach, to solve steady-state heat conduction, for cylindrical and planar geometries, with two sets of boundary conditions. Preliminary comparisons show that the proposed method achieves convergence with less mesh refinement than the finite difference method. This is possible as

- the presented approach takes advantage of the analytical expression of the heat flux for basic geometries (e.g., cylinders, slabs and potentially spheres, too);

- the Fourier's law is inverted through a simple procedure, which consists in (1) applying the Kirchhoff transformation, over a set of discrete points, (2) computing the integral average of the thermal conductivity by a quadrature formula, (3) using fixed-point iterations to update the temperature at the current node.

The method can be easily generalized to non-uniform volumetric sources, as well as to any integrable 1D power distribution. Future endeavours will focus on testing a large set of thermal conductivity laws, the possibility to extend the method to time-dependent simulations and ultimately the implementation in the multiphysics CEA platform.

APPENDIX A.

A finite-difference model has been considered for numerical comparisons. The approach consists in solving the heat equation for the temperature. The calculation nodes are located at the centre of each mesh. The average heat transfer coefficient between two consecutive meshes is modelled according to the series resistance rule as $\lambda_{n-1,n} = \frac{2 \cdot k_{n-1} k_n}{k_{n-1} \Delta_{n-1} + k_n \Delta_n}$, where Δ_n is the thickness of the mesh of index n , with $n = 0, \dots, N - 1$ (Fig. 6). At the domain border, where the temperature is imposed, the exchange coefficient is given by $\frac{2 \cdot k_N h}{2 \cdot k_n + h \Delta_N}$, h [$\frac{W}{m^2 \cdot ^\circ C}$] being provided by the user. If a null-flux boundary condition is imposed, the exchange coefficient is set to 0.

Figure 6. Series resistance model, where T_{n-1} and T_n are temperatures of node $n - 1$ and n , Δ_{n-1} and Δ_n the mesh sizes, k_{n-1} and k_n the thermal conductivities and $\frac{1}{\lambda_{n-1,n}}$ the equivalent thermal resistance.

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